

1 **Enterovirus D-68 infection in human primary airway and brain organoids: no**
2 **additional role for heparan sulfate binding for neurotropism**

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20 **Abstract:** Enterovirus D-68 (EV-D68) is an RNA virus that can cause outbreaks of acute flaccid
21 paralysis (AFP), a polio-like disease. Before 2010, EV-D68 was a rare pathogen associated with

22 mild respiratory symptoms but the recent EV-D68 related increase in severe respiratory illness
23 and outbreaks of AFP is not yet understood. An explanation for the rise in severe disease may be
24 due to changes in the viral genome resulting in neurotropism. In this regard, in addition to sialic
25 acid, binding to heparan sulfate proteoglycans (HSPGs) has been identified as a feature for viral
26 entry of some EV-D68 strains in cell lines. Studies in human primary organotypic cultures that
27 recapitulate human physiology will address the relevance of these HSPG-binding mutations for
28 EV-D68 infection *in vivo*. Therefore, in this work, we studied the replication and neurotropism
29 of previously determined sialic acid-dependent and HSPG-dependent strains using primary
30 human airway epithelial (HAE) cultures and induced human pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived
31 brain organoids. All three strains (B2/2042, B2/947, and A1/1348) used in this study infected
32 HAE cultures and human brain organoids (shown for the first time). Receptor blocking
33 experiments in both cultures confirm that B2/2042 infection is solely dependent on sialic acid
34 while B2/947 and A1/1348 (HSPG to a lesser extent) binds to sialic acid and HSPG for cell
35 entry. Our data suggest that HSPG-binding can be used by EV-D68 for entry in human
36 physiological models but offers no advantage for EV-D68 infection of brain cells.

37 **Importance:** Recent outbreaks of enterovirus D68, a non-polio enterovirus is associated with a
38 serious neurological condition in young children, acute flaccid myelitis (AFM). As there is no
39 antiviral treatment or a vaccine available for EV-D68 it is important to better understand how
40 EV-D68 causes AFM and why only recent outbreaks are associated with AFM. We investigated
41 if a change in receptor usage of EV-D68 increases the virulence of EV-D68 in the airway or the
42 central nervous system and thus could explain the increase in AFM cases. We studied this using
43 physiologically relevant human airway epithelium and cerebral organoid cultures that are
44 physiologically relevant human models. Our data suggest that heparan sulfate proteoglycans can

45 be used by EV-D68 as an additional entry receptor in human physiological models but offers no
46 advantage for EV-D68 infection of brain cells, and our data shows the potential of these46
47 innovative models for virology.

48 **Introduction**

49 The human Enterovirus D-68 (EV-D68) is a single-stranded positive-sense RNA virus from
50 the Enterovirus (EV) genus in the *Picornaviridae* family. EV-D68 was first isolated in 1962 in
51 California from children with respiratory infections (1). It remained a rare pathogen that caused
52 mild respiratory disease but since 2010 there has been an increased association with severe
53 respiratory illness and since 2014, outbreaks of acute flaccid paralysis (AFP) have been linked to
54 EV-D68 infection (2, 3). With the near global eradication of poliomyelitis, emergence of AFP
55 with clinical resemblance to poliomyelitis caused by other non-polio enteroviruses is a serious
56 concern (4).

57
58 The reasons behind this increase in pathogenicity of EV-D68 at both the airway (primary
59 site for entry and replication) and central nervous system (CNS, secondary site of infection) is
60 not clear. Increased pathogenicity could be due to a general increase in virulence leading to more
61 severe infections and higher rates of neurological complications (5). Contemporary strains might
62 have acquired the ability to bind different or additional receptors that enable a broader cell
63 tropism or more efficient infection of the primary and secondary infection sites. Indeed, in
64 addition to α 2,3- and α 2,6-linked sialic acids, some contemporary strains are also capable of cell
65 entry by binding ICAM-5 or sulfated glycosaminoglycans (sGAGs) which may play a role in
66 increased virulence (6, 7) (8) (9) (10). However, since ICAM-5 is not expressed in the human
67 respiratory tract or spinal cord, the role of ICAM-5 in increasing EV-D68 virulence is disputed
68 (5).

69

70 Cell surface endocytosis receptors such as sGAGs, and heparan sulfate proteoglycans
71 (HSPGs), in particular, are interesting as HSPG is known to play a role in binding of other
72 neurotropic viruses such as herpes simplex virus, dengue virus, and some echoviruses (11-15).
73 Moreover, HSPG-dependence through an intra-host adaptation resulting in neurovirulence has
74 been demonstrated for enterovirus A71 (EV-A71) (16, 17). The HSPG-binding mutation (L97R
75 in the VP1 region) was not present in EV-A71 respiratory isolates but only found in isolates from
76 feces, blood, and cerebrospinal fluid. This HSPG-binding mutation was also shown to modulate
77 *ex vivo* tissue tropism and was concluded to promote viral dissemination and neurotropism of
78 EV-A71 (16, 17). In a similar manner, HSPG-binding mutations could promote virulence and
79 neurotropism of EV-D68.

80
81 Although the HSPG-binding mutation in EV-D68 (E271K in the VP1 region) was
82 initially discovered through a cell culture adaptation, the HSPG-binding mutation at this position
83 is also found in some clinical isolates (7, 18-21). Moreover, work performed on a neuroblastoma
84 cell line showed an increased replication and attachment of EV-D68 HSPG-binding variants.
85 Evaluating the use of these receptors using human organotypic cultures will provide more insight
86 into *in vivo* pathogenesis as these complex cultures have better value for translational studies
87 over traditionally used cell lines (22). The primary replication site (airway) of EV-D68 infection
88 can be modelled using human airway epithelial cultures that closely mimic *in vivo* tissue in
89 respect to multicellular composition, epithelial function, and innate immune responses and have
90 been extensively used in virology for pathogenesis and antiviral studies (23-27). The secondary
91 replication site can be modelled using human induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived
92 cerebral organoids that closely resemble the developing human brain and have been used for

93 studying neurotropic viruses (28, 29). We, and others, previously characterized that these iPSC-
94 derived cerebral organoids contain various brain cells including neural progenitor cells, neurons,
95 and astrocytes (30, 31). Therefore, in this study, we assessed the roles of sialic acid and HSPG
96 for the infection of HAE and cerebral organoid cultures with three different contemporary EV-
97 D68 strains that use different receptors for entry in cell lines (B2/2042, solely dependent on sialic
98 acid for entry, and B2/947 and A1/1348 using sialic acid and another non-sialic acid receptor for
99 entry) (10).

100 **Results**

101 **EV-D68 replicates efficiently in human airway epithelial (HAE) cultures.**

102 The replication of one sialic acid-dependent strain (B2/2042) and two (B2/947 and
103 A1/1348) strains using sialic acid and one other receptor was tested by apical infection of HAE
104 cultures derived from three different donors (9) (10). We observed that all three strains were able
105 to replicate in HAE cultures (*Fig. 1A*) and the increase over 48 hours post infection (hpi) was
106 statistically significant, as measured by reverse transcription quantitative polymerase chain
107 reaction (RT-qPCR), while no viral RNA was measured in mock infected organoids. Tissue
108 culture infectious dose 50 (TCID50) analyses demonstrated that EV-D68 infection resulted in
109 significant production of infectious viral particles at 48 hpi of all three strains (*Fig. 1B*). Based
110 on the TCID50 data, the viral release was seen primarily on the apical side with undetectable
111 levels on the basolateral compartment of the HAE cultures (*data not shown*).

112 **EV-D68 can use HSPG as a second receptor in HAE cultures.**

113 Sialic acid-dependence in human airway was tested by pretreating the HAE cultures, prior
114 to viral infection, with neuraminidase which hydrolyzes α 2,3-, α 2,6-, and α 2,8-linked sialic acids

115 on the cell surface. HSPG-dependence was tested by pretreating the virus, prior to inoculation of
116 HAE, with soluble heparin to block the heparan sulfate (HS) binding sites on the viral capsid.
117 Neuraminidase treatment to remove sialic acid resulted in fewer viral RNA at 8 hpi for all three
118 EV-D68 strains confirming that all strains can use sialic acid for entry (*Fig 2.*). Heparin
119 treatment of the three strains of EV-D68 resulted in inhibition of B2/947 and to a lesser extent of
120 A1/1348 while having no effect on B2/2042.

121 **EV-D68 infection depletes ciliated cells in the human airway epithelium.**

122 To determine the cell tropism of EV-D68, we performed imaging with immunofluorescent
123 staining and confocal microscopy of the HAE cultures. The cultures were fixed and tripled
124 stained for ciliated cell marker β -tubulin, basal cell marker p63, and EV-D68 VP1 protein or
125 triple stained for secretory cell marker MUC5B, basal cell marker p63, and EV-D68 VP1
126 protein. At 8 hpi, viral staining was co-localized in ciliated cells (*Fig. 3*). Neuraminidase
127 treatment of the HAE cultures resulted in fewer EV-D68 B2/2042 virus positive cells while
128 heparin treatment of EV-D68 resulted in fewer virus-positive cells of the B2/947 and A1/1348
129 strains. Confocal imaging of the stained HAE inserts at 72 hpi revealed that EV-D68 A1/1348
130 and B2/2042 infection resulted in a depletion of ciliated cells while the ciliated cells remained
131 intact in EV-D68 B2/947 and MOCK infected cultures (*Fig. 4*). However, co-localization of
132 VP1-staining could not be observed at 72 hours post-infection. HAE infection with the three EV-
133 D68 strains did not affect the basal cells and no co-localization of VP1 staining with p63 staining
134 was observed. Although the HAE cultures had good mucus coverage on the cell surface,
135 MUC5B staining of secretory cells was inconclusive and MUC5B positive cells were not
136 observed in most of the cultures.

137 **EV-D68 infects human iPSC-derived cerebral organoids**

138 To assess whether EV-D68 is able to infect cerebral organoids and if the infection is
139 dependent on HSPG-binding, we infected four different batches of 45 to 52 days old cerebral
140 organoids with the three EV-D68 strains (B2/2042, B2/947, and A1/1348). We observed that all
141 three strains were able to infect the cerebral organoids as an increase in viral RNA was measured
142 in the medium of infected cerebral organoids and not in mock infected organoids by RT-qPCR
143 over time (*Fig. 5a*). TCID50 analyses showed a significant increase in infectious virus for all
144 strains in the medium at 48 hpi and not in mock infected organoids (*Fig. 5b*).

145 **EV-D68 can use HSPG as a second receptor in cerebral organoids**

146 Next, we investigated the receptor usage of the different strains in brain organoids by
147 either pretreating brain organoids with neuraminidase or pretreating the virus, prior to
148 inoculation, with soluble heparin to block HSPG-binding sites on the viral capsid. In line with
149 the results in HAE, B2/2042 replication was dependent on sialic acid, as neuraminidase
150 pretreatment reduced the viral fold change significantly ($P > 0.01$), while heparin treatment did
151 not inhibit replication (*Fig. 6*). For the other two strains, blocking of sialic acid as an entry
152 receptor also inhibited replication, but not significantly. EV-D68 strain A1/1348 was similarly
153 inhibited by blocking of HSPG as sialic acid removal, while the EV-D68 strain B2/947 was most
154 strongly inhibited by blocking of HSPG. However, due to high variation in fold changes between
155 each cerebral organoid, no significant reduction of viral replication was observed.

156 **Discussion**

157 In this study, we provide insights into EV-D68 receptor usage in primary organotypic cell
158 culture models. Given the importance of various cell entry receptors for picornavirus tropism, we
159 evaluated if HSPG-binding as previously identified using cell lines confer any benefits in human

160 primary cell culture. This HSPG-binding mutation (E271K in VP1 of EV-D68) was particularly
161 interesting as similar HSPG-binding mutations (L97R in VP1 of EV-A71) have been shown to
162 promote viral dissemination and neurotropism for another enterovirus, EV-A71 (16, 17).
163 Moreover, as HSPG are ubiquitously expressed across most tissues in humans, our hypothesis
164 was that the ability to bind HSPG could broaden the tropism for EV-D68.

165
166 Specific characteristics of HSPG and other sGAGs as having a net negative charge and
167 interacting electrostatically with a virus are well defined (32, 33). However, the role of HSPG-
168 binding and increased virulence is controversial (34). HSPG-binding is often described as a
169 result of cell culture adaptation that enhances viral infection *in vitro* (35). For respiratory viruses,
170 the ability to bind HSPG and other sGAGs is likely to be detrimental as the airway mucus is
171 abundant with sGAGs (36). Moreover, we did not see any differences in cell tropism between
172 HSPG-binding and non HSPG-binding strains in the airway. Although HSPG is diffusely
173 expressed throughout HAE cultures, both types of strains only infected the ciliated cells
174 consistent with EV-D68 infection of airway cultures (23, 37). This alone does not preclude the
175 usefulness of HSPG-binding for EV-D68 *in vivo*. We did not study if the HSPG-binding
176 mutation of EV-D68 alters the immune response upon infection and altered immune responses
177 could influence immune evasion. In a cell line the ability to bind sGAGs was already shown to
178 be beneficial for EV-D68 B2/947 infection. By binding sGAGs, EV-D68 could bypass
179 PLA2G16 facilitated delivery of viral RNA into the cytoplasm which could potentially alter
180 downstream immune responses (9). Thus, it would be interesting to see if any alterations to
181 innate immune response arises due to HSPG-binding in primary cell cultures.

182

183 HSPG-binding mutations may also be relevant for *in vivo* pathogenesis even if they do not
184 necessarily confer benefits at the primary replication site. As seen with EV-A71, an intra-host
185 emergence of HSPG-binding mutants might confer neurovirulence. Therefore, we evaluated
186 CNS infection of the different EV-D68 strains using cerebral organoids. Consistent with our
187 findings in the HAE cultures, all three strains were able to infect cerebral organoids. Contrary to
188 our initial expectation, HSPG-binding did not appear to promote neurotropism of EV-D68 and
189 some EV-D68 strains could use HSPG-binding for infection of cerebral organoids. For this
190 study, we employed human cerebral organoids as an infection model for EV-D68 infection of the
191 CNS in humans and show that EV-D68 can infect the brain. However, it is important to note that
192 currently there is no evidence that EV-D68 infects brain cells *in vivo*. The next step in this
193 research would be to evaluate EV-D68 infectivity in recently developed human iPSC-derived
194 motor neuron organoids, spinal cord organoids, or cortico-motor assembloids as models for EV-
195 D68 induced AFP (38-41).

196
197 In our study, we tested the possibility that HSPG-binding would result in neurovirulence of
198 EV-D68. It is possible that EV-D68 strains have other mutations that result in a phenotype with a
199 broader cell tropism (42, 43). For instance, contemporary strains have a contraction of the spacer
200 in the 5' untranslated region of the viral RNA. This specific site is an established region of
201 virulence in poliovirus and other picornaviruses (44-46). However, both contemporary and pre-
202 outbreak isolates of EV-D68 can replicate in neuronal cell lines as well in primary neurons and
203 astrocytes derived from human pluripotent stem cells (hPSCs) indicating that this contraction of
204 the spacer might not be responsible for increased virulence (47). Another possibility is the ability
205 of contemporary strains to replicate (*in vitro* on cell lines) at equal efficiency at 32°C or 37°C,

206 while the replication of prototype strains such as the EV-D68 Fermon strain (isolated from a
207 respiratory sample in 1962) is attenuated at higher temperatures (48). It would be worthwhile to
208 verify these findings using complex 3D CNS models, such as motor neuron or spinal cord
209 models.

210
211 In conclusion, in our experiments we did not obtain evidence that usage of HSPG as an
212 additional receptor by EV-D68 has additional benefits in physiological human models of the
213 primary and secondary replication sites. It is possible that HSPG-binding is a cell culture
214 adaptation and is most likely not the reason for the sudden emergence or neurotropism of
215 contemporary EV-D68 strains (10). Further research using clinical EV-D68 isolates from AFP
216 affected patients and novel human 3D CNS (motor neuron or spinal cord) models is necessary to
217 exclude the role of HSPG and sGAGs for EV-D68 neuroinfection *in vivo*.

218 **Materials and Methods**

219 Viruses and cells

220 EV-D68 strains B2/2042 (4310902042, isolated from a 1-year-old male diagnosed with
221 bronchiolitis), B2/947 (4310900947, isolated from a 22-year-old female diagnosed with
222 influenza-like illness); this strain acquired E271K mutation during initial passage in RD cells
223 (10), and A1/1348 (4310901348, isolated from a 36-year-old male diagnosed with common cold)
224 were obtained from the National Institute of Public Health and the Environment (RIVM, The
225 Netherlands). All strains were isolated in RD cells. EV-D68 B2/2042 was continued on RD cells
226 (human rhabdomyosarcoma; ATCC, USA) while B2/947 and A1/1348 were cultured in HeLa
227 cells (human adenocarcinoma; ATCC, USA). All cell lines were maintained in Eagle's minimum
228 essential medium (EMEM; Lonza, Switzerland) supplemented with L-glutamine (200 nM;

229 Lonza, Switzerland), penicillin/streptomycin (100 U/mL each; Lonza, Switzerland), non-
230 essential amino acids (ScienCell Research Laboratories, Canada), and fetal bovine serum
231 (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany). The 50% tissue culture infective dose (TCID₅₀) of virus was
232 determined in RD cells using the Reed and Muench method (49). Viral stocks were sequenced
233 prior to infection and B2/947 was confirmed to have the E271K mutation in VP1 while B2/2042
234 and A1/1348 did not have this strain-specific HSPG-binding mutation.

235

236 Human Airway Epithelial (HAE) cultures

237 HAE nasal MucilAir™ cultures derived from three individual donors (see *table 1* for
238 donor information) were purchased from Epithelix Sàrl (Switzerland). The inserts were cultured,
239 upon reception, for one week at an air-liquid interface before performing the infection
240 experiments. The HAE inserts were cultured in MucilAir™ culture medium (Epithelix Sàrl,
241 Switzerland) and the medium was refreshed every two to three days.

242

243 Infection of HAE cultures

244 All infection experiments were performed with one insert per condition with the three
245 different donors considered as biological replicates. Prior to infection, apical surfaces of the
246 HAE cultures were washed thrice with 200 µL Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS;
247 ThermoFisher Scientific, USA). HAE cultures were then inoculated with EV-D68 by adding 50
248 µL of virus stock (B2/947 6.1 logTCID₅₀/mL, A1/1348 6.36 logTCID₅₀/mL and B2/2042 4.86
249 logTCID₅₀/ml as determined on RD99 cells) to the apical side (as this is the physiological side
250 of infection *in vivo*) and incubated for two hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. After two hours incubation,
251 virus inoculum was discarded, and the apical surface was washed thrice with HBSS. The RD cell

252 culture media was added to the apical side for MOCK infection. For time point 0h, 100 μ L of
253 HBSS was added to the apical side and incubated for ten min. After incubation, 100 μ L of HBSS
254 and 100 μ L of culture medium was collected from the apical and basolateral sides respectively.
255 For the other time points, 100 μ L of HBSS was first added to the apical side followed by a ten
256 min incubation prior to sample collection from the apical and basolateral sides. After each
257 sample collection from the basolateral side 100 μ L of fresh culture media was added to keep the
258 total volume at 600 μ L per insert.

259

260 Receptor blocking in HAE cultures

261 Apical surfaces of the HAE cultures were washed thrice with 200 μ L HBSS and the inserts
262 were transferred to a new 24-well plate. For sialic acid blocking, 50 μ L of neuraminidase
263 solution (1:50 ratio in HBSS) was added to the apical side and incubated for one hour. To ensure
264 complete hydrolyses of sialic acid, neuraminidase from *Arthrobacter ureafaciens* (Roche
265 diagnostics, Switzerland) and neuraminidase from *Clostridium perfringens* (New England
266 BioLabs, USA) were used in equal proportion. For inserts that were not part of the sialic acid
267 condition (untreated and heparin conditions), 50 μ L of HBSS was added to the apical side and
268 incubated for one hour. In parallel, for blocking HSPG, virus stock was incubated with a working
269 concentration of 5 mg/mL heparin sodium salt (H4784; Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) dissolved in
270 phosphate buffered saline (PBS; Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) or equal amount of PBS for untreated
271 and neuraminidase conditions at 37°C, 5% CO₂. After one hour, inserts were washed once with
272 100 μ L HBSS and inoculated with 50 μ L of virus or virus/heparin solution. For MOCK inserts,
273 HBSS or media/heparin solution was used depending on the condition. The virus was inoculated
274 for two hours and sample collection at time point 0 and 8h were performed as described earlier.

275 As complete receptor blocking would not be possible, we analyzed the fold change in viral
276 copies between the 0 and 8 hpi, reflecting the first replication cycle for picornaviruses when the
277 receptor blocking effect will be most prominent.

278

279 Immunofluorescence staining and confocal microscopy of HAE cultures

280 Inserts were washed thrice apically and basolaterally with HBBS at the end time point (72h
281 for infection, 8h for receptor blocking). The inserts were then fixed with 4% formalin (Sigma-
282 Aldrich, Germany) in PBS for 30 min at room temperature (RT). Membranes from the HAE
283 inserts were then excised and submerged in 0.1% Triton X-100 for 15 min at RT to permeabilize
284 the cells. Following permeabilization, membranes were treated with a solution containing 0.5%
285 Tween20 (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) and 10% bovine serum albumin (BSA; Sigma-Aldrich,
286 Germany) in PBS and incubated overnight at 4°C to block non-specific binding of antibodies in
287 the subsequent steps. Between the fixation, permeabilization, and blocking steps, the membranes
288 were washed thrice with PBS. Membranes were then cut into two equal pieces before treating the
289 inserts with primary and secondary antibodies. All antibodies were diluted in a solution
290 containing 0.5% Tween20 and 3% BSA dissolved in PBS. For primary antibody staining,
291 membranes were incubated at 4°C overnight followed by washing thrice with 0.5% Tween20 in
292 PBS. Secondary antibody staining was performed for one hour at RT. The following primary
293 antibodies were used in different combinations – mouse monoclonal β -tubulin-Cy3 (128K4872,
294 Sigma-Aldrich, USA), mouse monoclonal mucin 5B (sc-393952, Santa Cruz Biotechnology,
295 USA), goat polyclonal p63 (AF1916, R&D systems, USA), and rabbit polyclonal EV-D68 VP1
296 (GTX132313, GeneTex, USA). After secondary antibody staining, membranes were mounted on
297 objective slides with ProLong™ Gold Antifade Mountant with DAPI (P36931, ThermoFisher

298 Scientific, USA). Mounted membranes were imaged using Leica TCS SP8 X microscope (Leica
299 Microsystems, Germany) and images were analyzed using Leica LAS X software (Leica
300 Microsystems, Germany).

301

302 Cerebral organoid cultures

303 Human iPSCs, IMR90-4 (WiCell, USA) were cultured in mTesr⁺ medium (STEMCELL
304 Technologies, Canada) on vitronectin (STEMCELL Technologies, Canada)-coated six-well
305 plates and were passaged using ReLeSR (STEMCELL Technologies, Canada). Cerebral
306 organoids were made from these iPSCs, using the cerebral organoid kit from STEMCELL
307 Technologies. In short, 9000 iPSCs were seeded per well in a round-bottom ultra-low-attachment
308 plate (Corning, USA). Embryonic bodies (EBs) formed and were differentiated into cerebral
309 organoids according to protocol and matured in a six-well plate while shaking on an orbital
310 shaker (INFORS, Switzerland) at 66 rpm at 37°C and 5% CO₂. With this protocol, four batches
311 of organoids were made from the same iPSC line but with different passage numbers.

312

313 Infection and receptor blocking of cerebral organoids

314 Cerebral organoid infection was performed on one batch of 45-day old organoids and three
315 batches of 52-day old organoids. Prior to infection, cerebral organoids were transferred to an
316 ultra-low-attachment 96-well plate (Corning, USA) and organoid maturation medium
317 (STEMCELL Technologies, Canada) was removed from the wells. For sialic acid blocking, 50
318 µL of neuraminidase solution (1:50 ratio in organoid maturation medium), all other organoids
319 were incubated in 50 µL organoid maturation medium. After one hour, organoids were washed
320 once with 200 µL organoid maturation medium, medium was removed and organoids were

321 inoculated with 50 μ L of virus (B2/947 4.8 logTCID50/mL, A1/1348 7 logTCID50/ml or
322 B2/2042 6.25 logTCID50/ml) that was pre-incubated at 37°C for 1 hour with or without 5
323 mg/mL heparin sodium salt dissolved in phosphate buffered saline. or virus pretreated with
324 heparin. Inoculated cerebral organoids were then incubated for one hour at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Then,
325 inoculum was removed, and the organoids were washed thrice with DMEM. After the third
326 wash, the organoids were transferred to a 48-well plate, 500 μ l of organoid maturation medium
327 was added and the organoids were incubated at 37°C, 5% CO₂. After one hour (t₀), 24, 48 and 72
328 hpi, the medium was sampled and refreshed with 500 μ l maturation medium. Samples were
329 stored at -80°C.

330

331 EV-D68 detection by RT-qPCR and TCID50

332 25 μ L of collected culture medium was lysed and RNA was extracted using the MagNA
333 Pure LC instrument (Roche Diagnostics, Switzerland) and the MagNA Pure LC Total Nucleic
334 Acid Isolation Kit (03038505001, Roche Diagnostics, Switzerland) as per the manufacturer's
335 instructions. 40 μ L of the 50 μ L RNA eluate was reverse transcribed as described earlier (50). 5
336 μ L of cDNA was then used for RT-qPCR and analyzed using LightCycler® 480 (Roche
337 diagnostics, Switzerland) as per the manufacturer's instructions with the EV-D68 primers
338 (Forward: 5'-TGT TCC CAC GGT TGA AAA CAA -3'; Reverse: 5'-TGT CTA GCG TCT CAT
339 GGT TTT CAC -3'; Biogio, The Netherlands) and probes (probe 1: 6-FAM- ACC GCT ATA
340 GTA CTT CG –MGB NFQ; Probe 2: 6-FAM- TCC GCT ATA GTA CTT CG –MGB NFQ;
341 Biogio, The Netherlands). For cerebral organoid medium samples: 25 μ L of collected culture
342 medium was lysed and RNA was extracted using the Purelink RNA Mini kit (Invitrogen) as per
343 the manufacturer's instructions. 40 μ L of the 60 μ L RNA eluate was reverse transcribed as

344 described earlier (50). For TCID₅₀, 25 µL of collected culture medium was serially diluted 1:10
345 in E8 medium. 50 µL of diluted sample was added to 150 µL of RD99 cell suspension in
346 quadruplicates in a 96-well plate and incubated at 37°C, 5% CO₂. After 7 days, the plates were
347 scored and the titer was calculated via the Reed Muench method.

348

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481 **Figure and table legends**

482 **Fig 1. Replication of different EV-D68 strains in human airway epithelial (HAE) cultures.**

483 (A) Growth curves for EV-D68 strains in the HAE model. Viral RNA was measured by RT-
484 qPCR analysis of the culture medium at specified time points. (B) Replication competent viral
485 titers were measured using a medium tissue culture infectious dose 50 (TCID50) assay. The
486 geometric mean and standard deviation of three biological replicates are shown in both panels. In
487 panel B, P values were calculated by Sidak's multiple comparison test. (*P<0.05, **P<0.01,
488 ***P>0.001, n=3 biological replicates). For mock infected HAE cultures, no increase in viral
489 RNA was measured.

490 **Fig 2. Receptor usage of different EV-D68 strains in HAE cultures**

491 The fold change in viral RNA copies at 8 hpi, normalized to 0 hpi, in medium of EV-D68
492 infected HAE cultures where the binding to sialic acid receptor was blocked by neuraminidase
493 and binding to HSPG was blocked using soluble heparin while untreated HAE were infected
494 with EV-D68 without either treatment. Viral RNA was measured by RT-qPCR analysis of the
495 culture medium at 0 and 8 hpi. For B2/2042 and A1/1348, the results are based on three
496 biological replicates. For B2/947 two biological replicates are shown as the replication cycle was
497 too slow in the third donor and therefore, no replication was yet observed after 8 hpi based on the
498 replication curves in Figure 1. For mock infected HAE cultures, no increase in viral RNA was
499 measured.

500 **Fig 3. Immunofluorescent staining of EV-D68 infection of HAE cultures 8 hpi.**

501 Immunofluorescent staining of EV-D68 infection of HAE cultures 8 hpi under different
502 conditions. EV-D68 (green) is co-localized in ciliated cells (red). The basal cells were present in

503 a different plane and remained uninfected. A 3D side view of the confocal z-stack is shown in
504 supplementary figure 3. Scale bars, 50 μm .

505 **Fig 4. Immunofluorescent staining of EV-D68 infection of HAE cultures 72 hpi.**

506 EV-D68 A1/1348 and B2/2042 infection disrupts cell monolayer as seen by depletion of infected
507 ciliated cells (red) on the apical side (top row). No EV-D68 staining (green) was seen at 72 hpi
508 likely due to death of susceptible cells which was consistent with the growth curves in fig 1A.
509 The basal cells (purple) were in a different plane (*bottom row*) and remained unaffected. Scale
510 bars, 50 μm .

511 **Fig 5. Replication of different EV-D68 strains in cerebral organoids**

512 (A) Growth curves for EV-D68 strains in cerebral organoids. Viral RNA was measured by RT-
513 qPCR analysis of the culture medium at specified time points. (n=4 batches) (B) Replication
514 competent viral titers were measured using a medium tissue culture infectious dose (TCID₅₀)
515 assay. (Limit of detection (L.O.D.), n=1 batch of 5 organoids). The geometric mean and 95%
516 confidence interval are shown in both panels. P values were calculated by Sidak's multiple
517 comparison test. (**P<0.01, ***P>0.001).

518 **Fig 6. Receptor use of different EV-D68 strains in cerebral organoids**

519 The fold change in viral RNA copies in medium of EV-D68 infected cerebral organoids where
520 the binding to sialic acid was blocked by neuraminidase and binding to HSPG by soluble heparin
521 while untreated cerebral organoids were infected with EV-D68 without neuraminidase or heparin
522 treatment. Viral RNA was measured by RT-qPCR analysis of the culture medium at 0 and 48
523 hpi, fold change was calculated by normalizing viral to t₀. (each dot represents an individual
524 organoid originating from 3 batches of organoids, geometric mean and geometric standard
525 deviation are shown. P values were calculated by Sidak's multiple comparison test (**P<0.01).

Table 1. Donor information for HAE cultures

Donor	Age	Sex	Race	Smoker?	Pathology
MD048401	55	Male	Caucasian	Non-smoker	No pathology reported
MD0043601	46	Male	Caucasian	Non-smoker	No pathology reported
MD019702	45	Male	Unknown	Unknown	No pathology reported

Cilia EV-D68 VP1 DAPI

947

1348

2042

MOCK

Cilia EV-D68 DAPI

Basal cells

A

